

On micro forms of Δ -open sets, Δ -continuous maps and generalized micro Δ -continuous in micro topological spaces

Selvaraj Ganesan^{1*}

¹PG & Research Department of Mathematics,
Raja Doraisingam Government Arts College, Sivagangai-630561, Tamil Nadu, India.
(Affiliated to Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Tamil Nadu, India). ORCID iD: [0000-0002-7728-8941](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7728-8941)

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Abstract: This article introduces and studied $m\Delta$ -open sets in micro topological spaces. We offer a new class of sets called $gm\Delta$ -closed sets in micro topological spaces and we study some of its basic properties. The idea of introducing new classes of open sets are called micro semi Δ -open, micro α - Δ -open, micro pre Δ -open, micro b- Δ -open micro β - Δ -open, micro regular Δ -open sets, micro semi Δ -continuous, micro α - Δ -continuous, micro pre Δ -continuous, micro b- Δ -continuous micro β - Δ -continuous and micro regular Δ -continuous in micro topological spaces. We introduce $m\Delta$ -continuous maps, $gm\Delta$ -continuous maps, $m\Delta$ -irresolute maps, $gm\Delta$ -irresolute maps, contra $m\Delta$ -continuous maps and contra $gm\Delta$ -continuous maps in micro topological spaces and discuss some of their properties.

Key words: Δ -closed, $m\Delta$ -closed, $gm\Delta$ -closed, $gm\Delta$ -continuous maps, $gm\Delta$ -irresolute maps and contra $gm\Delta$ -continuous maps

1. Introduction

Several notions of open-like and closed-like sets in micro topological spaces were introduced and studied. The beginning was with S. Chandrasekar who initiated the notion of micro forms of open sets, [1, 2]. After that micro β -open sets and micro b-open sets in micro topological spaces were introduced H. Z. Ibrahim, [7, 8]. Furthermore, the notions of micro regular open sets and micro π -open sets were initiated, [3]. We introduced and studied the notion of micro Δ -open sets in micro topological spaces,[5]. The concept of micro continuity in micro topological spaces was extended to generalized micro Δ -continuity, [6].

A set in a topological space is called Δ -open if it is the symmetric difference of two open sets. The notion of Δ -open sets appeared in [10] and in [4]. However, it was pointed out in [10] and in [4] that the notion of Δ -open sets is due to a preprint by M. Veera Kumar. The complement of a Δ -open set is Δ -closed.

A set in a micro topological space is called $m\Delta$ -open if it is the symmetric difference of two micro open sets were initiated, [5].

Preliminary concepts required in our work are briefly recalled in section 2. In section 3, the idea of introducing new classes of open sets are called micro semi Δ -open, micro α - Δ -open, micro pre Δ -open, micro b- Δ -open, micro β - Δ -open, micro regular Δ -open sets, micro semi Δ -continuous, micro α - Δ -continuous, micro pre Δ -continuous, micro b- Δ -continuous micro β - Δ -continuous and micro regular Δ -continuous in micro topological spaces and also the concept of $gm\Delta$ -continuous maps and $gm\Delta$ -irresolute maps. We introduce contra $gm\Delta$ -continuous map in micro topological spaces and discuss some of their properties.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [9] Let U be a non-empty finite set of objects called the universe and R be an equivalence relation on U named as the indiscernibility relation. Elements in the same equivalence class are indiscernible. The pair (U, R) is said to be the approximation space. Let $X \subseteq U$.

1. The lower approximation of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be for certain classified as X with respect to R and it is denoted by $L_R(X)$.

That is, $L_R(X) = \bigcup x \in U \{R(x) : R(x) \subseteq X\}$ where $R(x)$ denotes the equivalence class determined by x .

2. The upper approximation of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be possibly classified as X with respect to R and it is denoted by $U_R(X)$.

That is, $U_R(X) = \bigcup x \in U \{R(x) : R(x) \cap X \neq \emptyset\}$

3. The boundary region of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be neither in nor as not- X with respect to R and it is denoted by $B_R(X)$. That is, $B_R(X) = U_R(X) - L_R(X)$

Definition 2.2. [9] If $(U, \tau_R(X))$ is the nano topological space with respect to X where $X \subseteq U$ and if $A \subseteq U$, then

1. The nano interior of the set A is defined as the union of all nano open subsets contained in A and it is denoted by $\text{nint}(A)$. That is, $\text{nint}(A)$ is the largest nano open subset of A .
2. The nano closure of the set A is defined as the intersection of all nano closed sets containing A and it is denoted by $\text{ncl}(A)$. That is, $\text{ncl}(A)$ is the smallest nano closed set containing A .

Definition 2.3. [1] Let $(U, \tau_R(X))$ be a nano topological space. Then, $\mu_R(X) = \{N \cup (\dot{N} \cap \mu) : N, \dot{N} \in \tau_R(X) \text{ and } \mu \notin \tau_R(X)\}$ is called the Micro topology on U with respect to X . The triplet $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ is called Micro topological space and the elements of $\mu_R(X)$ are called Micro open sets and the complement of a Micro open set is called a Micro closed set.

Definition 2.4. [1] The Micro interior of a set A is denoted by $\text{Micro-int}(A)$ (briefly, $\text{m-int}(A)$) and is defined as the union of all Micro open sets contained in A . i.e., $\text{Mic-int}(A) = \bigcup \{G : G \text{ is Micro open and } G \subseteq A\}$.

Definition 2.5. [1] The Micro closure of a set A is denoted by $\text{Micro-cl}(A)$ (briefly, $\text{m-cl}(A)$) and is defined as the intersection of all Micro closed sets containing A . i.e., $\text{Mic-cl}(A) = \bigcap \{F : F \text{ is Micro closed and } A \subseteq F\}$.

Definition 2.6. [4, 10, 11] A subset A of a space (X, τ) is called Δ -open if $A = (B - C) \cup (C - B)$, where B and C are open subsets of X . Δ -closed sets are the complement of Δ -open sets.

Definition 2.7. [5] A subset S of a space $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ is said to be micro Δ -open set (in short, $m\Delta$ -open) if $S = (A - B) \cup (B - A)$, where A and B are micro-open subsets in U . The complement of micro- Δ -open sets is called micro- Δ -closed sets.

Definition 2.8. [5] The micro interior of a set A is denoted by $\text{micro } \Delta\text{-int}(A)$ (briefly, $m\Delta\text{-int}(A)$) and is defined as the union of all $m\Delta$ open sets contained in A . i.e., $m\Delta\text{-int}(A) = \bigcup \{G : G \text{ is } m\Delta\text{-open and } G \subseteq A\}$.

Definition 2.9. [5] The micro closure of a set A is denoted by $\text{micro } \Delta\text{-cl}(A)$ (briefly, $m\Delta\text{-cl}(A)$) and is defined as the intersection of all $m\Delta$ -closed sets containing A . i.e., $m\Delta\text{-cl}(A) = \bigcap \{F : F \text{ is } m\Delta\text{-closed and } A \subseteq F\}$.

Definition 2.10. [6] A subset A of a space $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ is called a generalized micro Δ -closed (briefly, $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -closed) set if $m\Delta\text{cl}(A) \subseteq T$ whenever $A \subseteq T$ and T is $m\Delta$ -open in $(U, \tau_R(X))$. $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -open sets are the complement of $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -closed sets.

Proposition 2.1. [6] *Every $m\Delta$ -closed set is $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -closed but not conversely.*

Proof. Let A be a $m\Delta$ -closed set and T be any $m\Delta$ -open set containing A . Since A is $m\Delta$ -closed, we have $m\Delta\text{cl}(A) = A \subseteq T$. Hence A is $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -closed. \square

The converse of Proposition 2.1 need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 2.1. *Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1, 2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{2, 3\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, U\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1, 3\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -closed sets are $\{\phi, \{2\}, \{1, 3\}, U\}$ and $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -closed sets are $\{\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U\}$. Here, $H = \{1, 2\}$ is $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -closed set but it is not $m\Delta$ -closed.*

3. On Micro Forms of Δ -Open Sets, Continuous maps, $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -Continuous maps and $\text{gm-}\Delta$ -Irresolute maps

Definition 3.1. A subset S of a space $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ is called

1. micro semi- Δ -open set (in short, $ms\Delta$ -open) if $S = (A - B) \cup (B - A)$, where A and B are micro semi-open subsets in U .
2. micro α - Δ -open set (in short, $m\alpha\Delta$ -open) if $S = (A - B) \cup (B - A)$, where A and B are micro α -open subsets in U .
3. micro pre- Δ -open set (in short, $mp\Delta$ -open) if $S = (A - B) \cup (B - A)$, where A and B are micro pre-open subsets in U .
4. micro b- Δ -open set (in short, $mb\Delta$ -open) if $S = (A - B) \cup (B - A)$, where A and B are micro b-open subsets in U .
5. micro β - Δ -open set (in short, $m\beta\Delta$ -open) if $S = (A - B) \cup (B - A)$, where A and B are micro β -open subsets in U .
6. micro regular- Δ -open set (in short, $mr\Delta$ -open) if $S = (A - B) \cup (B - A)$, where A and B are micro regular-open subsets in U .

The complements of the above mentioned micro Δ -open sets are called their respective micro $sm\Delta$ -closed sets.

Proposition 3.1. *Let $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ be micro topological spaces. Then*

1. *Every $m\Delta$ -open set is micro semi- Δ -open.*
2. *Every micro semi-open set is micro semi- Δ -open.*

But the converse implications are not true in general. Following is an example:

Example 3.1. Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{1\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, U\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 3\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro semi-open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$ and micro semi Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$. Here, $P = \{2, 3\}$ is micro semi Δ -open. But is neither $m\Delta$ -open nor micro semi-open.

Proposition 3.2. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ be micro topological spaces. Then

1. Every $m\Delta$ -open set is micro α - Δ -open.
2. Every $m\Delta$ -open set is micro pre Δ -open.
3. Every $m\Delta$ -open set is micro b - Δ -open.
4. Every $m\Delta$ -open set is micro β - Δ -open.
5. Every micro α - $m\Delta$ -open set is micro pre- Δ -open.
6. Every micro semi- Δ -open set is micro b - Δ -open.
7. Every micro α -open set is micro α - Δ -open.
8. Every micro pre-open set is micro pre Δ -open.
9. Every micro b -open set is micro b - Δ -open.
10. Every micro β -open set is micro β - Δ -open.
11. Every micro regular-open set is micro regular- Δ -open.

But the converse of above implications are not true in general. Following is an example:

Example 3.2. Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{1\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, U\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 3\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro α - Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro pre- Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro b - Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro β - Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro α -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$, micro pre-open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$, micro b -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$, micro β -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$. Here, (i) $Q = \{1, 2\}$ is micro α - Δ -open, micro pre Δ -open, micro b - Δ -open, micro β - Δ -open sets but is not $m\Delta$ -open. (ii) $R = \{2, 3\}$ is micro α - Δ -open, micro pre Δ -open, micro b - Δ -open, micro β - Δ -open sets. But is neither micro α -open nor micro pre-open nor micro b -open nor micro- β -open.

Example 3.3. Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1, 2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{2, 3\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, U\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1, 3\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$, micro α - Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$, micro pre- Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$. Here, $L = \{1, 2\}$ is micro pre- Δ -open. But is neither $m\Delta$ -open nor micro α - Δ -open.

Example 3.4. Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1, 2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{1, 3\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, U\}$. If $\mu = \{2, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{2, 3\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi,$

$\{1\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro semi- Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro b- Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$. Here, $M = \{1, 3\}$ is micro b- Δ -open. But is neither $m\Delta$ -open nor micro semi- Δ -open.

Example 3.5. Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{1\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, U\}$. If $\mu = \{2\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro regular- Δ -open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$, micro regular-open sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, U$. Here, $N = \{2, 3\}$ is micro regular- Δ -open sets but is not micro-regular-open.

Definition 3.2. A map $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ is called

1. $m\Delta$ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a $m\Delta$ -open set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
2. micro semi- Δ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a micro semi- Δ -open set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
3. micro α - Δ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a micro α - Δ -open set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
4. micro pre- Δ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a micro pre- Δ -open set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
5. micro b- Δ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a micro b- Δ -open set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
6. micro β - Δ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a micro β - Δ -open set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
7. micro regular- Δ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a micro regular- Δ -open set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ be micro topological spaces. Then

1. Every $m\Delta$ -continuous is micro semi- Δ -continuous but not conversely.
2. Every $m\Delta$ -continuous is micro α - Δ -continuous but not conversely.
3. Every $m\Delta$ -continuous is micro pre- Δ -continuous but not conversely.
4. Every $m\Delta$ -continuous is micro b- Δ -continuous but not conversely.
5. Every $m\Delta$ -continuous is micro β - Δ -continuous but not conversely.
6. Every micro α - $m\Delta$ -continuous is micro pre- Δ -continuous but not conversely.
7. Every micro semi- Δ -continuous is micro b- Δ -continuous but not conversely.
8. Every micro regular-continuous is micro regular- Δ -continuous but not conversely.

Proof. The proof follows from Proposition 3.1 and 3.2. □

Definition 3.3. A map $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ is called gm- Δ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a gm- Δ -closed set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -closed set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.

Theorem 3.2. *Every $m\Delta$ -continuous is gm- Δ -continuous but not conversely.*

Proof. The proof follows from Proposition 2.1. □

Theorem 3.3. *If $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ is gm- Δ -continuous and $g : (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)') \rightarrow (W, \tau_R(X)'', \mu_R(X)'')$ is $m\Delta$ - continuous then $g \circ f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_R(X)'', \mu_R(X)'')$ is gm- Δ -continuous.*

Proof. Let K be $m\Delta$ -closed set in W . Since g is $m\Delta$ -continuous, $g^{-1}(K)$ is $m\Delta$ -closed in V . Since f is gm- Δ -continuous, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(G) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(K))$ is gm- Δ -closed in U . Therefore $g \circ f$ is gm- Δ -continuous. □

Proposition 3.3. *A map $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ is gm- Δ -continuous if and only if $f^{-1}(G)$ is gm- Δ -open in $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G in $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.*

Proof. Let $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ be gm- Δ -continuous and G be an $m\Delta$ -open set in $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$. Then G^c is $m\Delta$ -closed in $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ and since f is gm- Δ -continuous, $f^{-1}(G^c)$ is gm- Δ -closed in $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$. But $f^{-1}(G^c) = f^{-1}((G)^c)$ and so $f^{-1}(G)$ is gm- Δ -open in $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$.

Conversely, assume that $f^{-1}(G)$ is gm- Δ -open in $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for each $m\Delta$ -open set G in $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$. Let F be a $m\Delta$ -closed set in $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$. Then F^c is $m\Delta$ -open in $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ and by assumption, $f^{-1}(F^c)$ is gm- Δ -open in $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$. Since $f^{-1}(F^c) = f^{-1}((F)^c)$, we have $f^{-1}(F)$ is $m\Delta$ -closed in $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ and so f is gm- Δ -continuous. □

Definition 3.4. A map $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ is called

1. $m\Delta$ -irresolute if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a micro semi Δ -closed set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every micro semi Δ -closed set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
2. gm- Δ -irresolute if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a gm- Δ -closed set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every gm- Δ -closed set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.

Example 3.6. *Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{1\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, U\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 3\}, U\}$. Then micro semi-closed sets are $\phi, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$ and micro semi Δ -closed sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$. Let $V = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $V/R = \{\{1, 2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{2, 3\}$. The micro topology $\tau_R(X)' = \{\phi, V\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X) = \{\phi, \{1, 3\}, V\}$. Then micro semi-closed sets are $\phi, \{2\}, V$ and micro semi Δ -closed sets are $\phi, \{2\}, \{1, 3\}, V$. Define $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ to be the identity map. Then f is $m\Delta$ -irresolute.*

Example 3.7. *Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1, 2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{2, 3\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, U\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1, 3\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$ and gm- Δ -closed sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$. Let $V = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with*

$V/R = \{\{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{1\}$. The micro topology $\tau_R(X)'$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, V\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 3\}, V\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, V$ and $gm\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, V$. Define $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ to be the identity map. Then f is $gm\Delta$ -irresolute.

Theorem 3.4. Every $gm\Delta$ -irresolute map is $gm\Delta$ -continuous but not conversely.

Proof. Let $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ be a $gm\Delta$ -irresolute map. Let G be a $m\Delta$ -closed set of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$. Then by the Proposition 2.1, G is $gm\Delta$ -closed. Since f is $gm\Delta$ -irresolute, then $f^{-1}(G)$ is a $gm\Delta$ -closed set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$. Therefore f is $gm\Delta$ -continuous. \square

Theorem 3.5. Let $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ and $g : (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)') \rightarrow (W, \tau_R(X)'')$ be two arbitrary maps. Then

1. $g \circ f$ is $gm\Delta$ -continuous if g is $m\Delta$ -continuous and f is $gm\Delta$ -continuous.
2. $g \circ f$ is $gm\Delta$ -irresolute if both f and g are $gm\Delta$ -irresolute.
3. $g \circ f$ is $gm\Delta$ -continuous if g is $gm\Delta$ -continuous and f is $gm\Delta$ -irresolute.

Proof. Omitted. \square

Definition 3.5. A map $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ is called

1. contra- $m\Delta$ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a $m\Delta$ -closed set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.
2. contra- $gm\Delta$ -continuous if $f^{-1}(G)$ is a $gm\Delta$ -closed set of $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$ for every $m\Delta$ -open set G of $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$.

Proposition 3.4. Every contra- $m\Delta$ -continuous is contra- $gm\Delta$ -continuous but not conversely.

Proof. Let $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ be a contra $m\Delta$ -continuous map and let G be any $m\Delta$ -open set in $(V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$. Then, $f^{-1}(G)$ is $m\Delta$ -closed in U . Since every $m\Delta$ -closed set is $gm\Delta$ -closed, $f^{-1}(G)$ is $gm\Delta$ -closed in U . Therefore f is contra- $gm\Delta$ -continuous. \square

Example 3.8. Let $U = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $U/R = \{\{1, 2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{2, 3\}$. The nano topology $\tau_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, U\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1, 3\}, U\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{2\}, \{1, 3\}, U$ and $gm\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, U$. Let $V = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with $V/R = \{\{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ and $X = \{1\}$. The micro topology $\tau_R(X)'$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, V\}$. If $\mu = \{1, 3\}$ then the micro topology $\mu_R(X)$ consists of $\{\phi, \{1\}, \{1, 3\}, V\}$. Then $m\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, V$ and $gm\Delta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}, V$. Define $f : (U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_R(X)', \mu_R(X)')$ to be the identity map. Then f is contra- $gm\Delta$ -continuous but not contra $m\Delta$ -continuous, since $f^{-1}(\{2, 3\}) = \{2, 3\}$ is not $m\Delta$ -closed in $(U, \tau_R(X), \mu_R(X))$.

Conclusion

In this article, the idea of introducing new classes of open-like sets micro semi Δ -open, micro α - Δ -open, micro pre- Δ -open, micro β - Δ -open, micro regular- Δ -open sets, micro semi Δ -continuous, micro α - Δ -continuous, micro pre- Δ -continuous, micro b- Δ -continuous micro β - Δ -continuous and micro regular- Δ -continuous in micro topological spaces We introduced $m\Delta$ -continuous maps, gm- Δ -continuous maps, $m\Delta$ -irresolute maps, gm- Δ -irresolute maps, contra $m\Delta$ -continuous maps and contra-gm- Δ -continuous maps in micro topological spaces and discuss some of their properties. In future, we have extended this work in various micro topological fields with some applications.

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